

Top Challenges Startups Face: A Literature Review

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Abstract

Establishing a startup business requires lots of effort, but when the focus is on the right side of the business the difficulties can be resolved fastly and efficiently, the paper will involve top challenges which startups face nowadays and tries to give info about the types of startups which make the most capital. In

This Literature Review online and exploratory research types of Surveys are used to deeply analyze the Startups well-being and also the weak points to develop.

Keywords: Indicators of Failure, SHELL Business Model, Market Competition

Startaplarning asosiy muammolari: Adabiyot sharhi

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Annotatsiya

Boshlang'ich biznesni tashkil etish juda ko'p kuch talab qiladi, ammo diqqat biznesning to'g'ri tomonida bo'lsa, qiyinchiliklarni tez va samarali hal qilish imkoniyati kelib chiqadi, maqola bugungi kunda startaplar duch keladigan asosiy muammolarni o'z ichiga oladi va startap turlari haqida ma'lumot berishga harakat qiladi. qaysi eng ko'p kapital qiladi.

Ushbu Adabiyotlar sharhida So'rovlarning onlayn va tadqiqot turlaridan Startaplarning farovonligini chuqur tahlil qilish va rivojlantirish uchun zaif tomonlardan foydalaniladi.

Kalit So'zlar: Muvaffaqiyatsizlik ko'rsatkichlari, SHELL biznes modeli, bozordagi raqobat

Главные проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются стартапы: Обзор литературы

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Аннотация

Создание стартап-бизнеса требует больших усилий, но когда фокус находится на правильной стороне бизнеса, трудности могут быть решены быстро и эффективно, статья будет включать основные проблемы, с которыми стартапы сталкиваются в настоящее время, и попытается дать информацию о типах стартапов, которые делают больше всего капитала. В этом обзоре литературы онлайн и поисковые типы исследований Опросы используются для глубокого анализа благополучия стартапов, а также слабых сторон для развития.

Ключевые слова: Индикаторы неудач, Бизнес-модель SHELL, Рыночная конкуренция

Introduction

Nowadays, establishing a new business or opening a startup might seem the easiest option to those who want to get rich really fast, but as times past competition in the business market is rapidly rising leaving startup runners with nothing but experience and empty wallets. However, there are a great number of startups which were at first catastrophic experience but after all enhancements and permanent developments startup owner's reached their peak in generating the revenue. In this Literature review there will be analyzed and summarized regardless of how startups are thought to be managed, still there are numerous issues and difficulties which awaits them at the end of a tunnel, below will be introduced and analyzed some of the recent and mostly encountered challenges that startups impinge.

Methodology

According to the Article **Startups Roads to Failure** (Marco Cantamessa, 2018), in order to understand the problem within the startup's performance there is a great tool to use which is a SHELL model, it helps businesses to identify the relationship and connection between the model's system and elements with the employees behaviour also their performance at work. The "S" means aspects which are non-physical, such as policies, processes and manuals; these factors show in what way the tasks should be done.

"H" means equipment, machines, and physical instruments which employees use. "E" refers to the social, organizational and physical conditions in which the workforce works. "L" meaning People refers to their performance while completing the given instructions including proficiency, acknowledgement, and confinement of the employees. The next "L" in the model represents Person to Person intercommunications and collaborations between humans.

Figure 1. The Model of SHELL (Marco Cantamessa, 2018)

Analysis of Studies (Literature Review)

As we now have an understanding of what the SHELL model refers to, it is time to move on to the next step which is implementation of the model to the startup businesses real action issues while trying to operate successfully. To identify the real problem in startups we will first focus on each section of a SHELL model, That is there are enough aspects in each section of a model which should not be considered as useless points to work on. These actions lead the startups to identify the failures which are considered as exemplary stereotypes

Figure 2. Startups Failures acclimatized by SHELL (Marco Cantamessa, 2018)

Business model of Startups which relates to the Software side of the SHELL tool helps to understand the weak points of a startup. First challenge when it comes to looking at the Business modules of Startups is that the businesses are lacking in traction of organization's profits and losses which may be a key factor in mislaying the competitive advantage in the potential market among its rival startup businesses.

Next big challenge is paying attention to the wrong vision of startups, in the beginning the company sets the original vision statement in order to achieve it in a short period of time, however if losing the original vision the plans of the company may collapse. 3rd Most faced challenge which startups face in the Business Model stage is positioning wrongly in the operating marketplace, it leads to rapidly decreased sales, customer interactions and ability to stay in front when the bankruptcy happens. One of the main challenges when it comes to the Hardware aspect (Product) is producing products which are not acceptable by the clients at all, the reason is that startups do not pay attention to manufactured goods in return the success will be unreachable due to the bad sales.

In the Environment stage the startups main problem is there are more than enough rival companies which operate in the same market and sell or provide exact similar services or products,

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-12

it may play a negative role in founding and guaranteeing the safety of the startup company among its competitors. Before the final stage (The Liveware) user and customer problems are considered one of the key components in startups success but there is a huge mistake which is made by companies while building a strong customer base, the customers who are unfaithful meaning the target audience is identified wrong which is why the interest is low towards the selling product or provided service by the startup businesses.

Finally, the last aspect of the startups internal challenge is running out of founded capital, in the business the cash is essential tool to establish and develop a new product line especially when it is a startup company which is beginning to enter to the new market, there are problems that are considered to be solved by the help of a good amount of money and as soon as this amount is found the rest is left to the management team to control.

Table 8 Indicators of Startups Failure (R. Bednar, 2017, p 238)

As it is shown in the table of the article **INDICATORS OF STARTUP FAILURE** (R. Bednar, 2017), there are established nearly 50 million fresh startup projects and companies annually that means 137,000 of them are considered as daily newcomers to the market also more than 75% of the all startups are created in USA which is not a huge surprise. According to the table above there are mainly 11 types of startups worldwide which are able to generate a good amount of revenue annually from Robotics field up to social applications business, it means that only 2% of the startups which are operated in Robotics, Payment systems and Food/Beverages are received a profit over the last 20 years, the startups which are focused on artificial intelligence and financial services are set around 3%, internet security and biotechnology peaked at 6%, data analysis

startups 7%, Interestingly most of the profits were earned by the software tools 30% and social application startups by the 37%.

Further directions and conclusions

As it was analyzed in the above Literature review, main challenges startups are considered to fail rely on how the business is managed and what tools also models are implemented during the establishment and further operation time, SHELL module can be a great example to understand these issues in order to liquidate them immediately. In the mentioned indicators of Startups failures it is clear that choosing the right and suitable sphere of business is essential to become one of the main key players in this modern consistently rising market, additionally looking into the flopping indicators gives a new potential chances for new established Startup company not to repeat the mistakes which were taken by their rivals.

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